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Experimental and Numerical Investigation of the Hydrodynamic Performance of an Oscillating Water Column Wave Energy Converter

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Highlights

The performance of an oscillating water column converter is investigated numerically and experimentally

The boundary integral equation method is implemented to solve the appropriate 2D boundary value problem

A comprehensive experimental campaign is carried out in both regular and irregular waves.

the efficiency is very sensitive to the variations in the turbine damping although the absolute maximum efficiency is less sensitive

influence of the wave height has less important than the other two parameters (turbine damping and incoming wave period)

35 1. Introduction

36 Ocean wave energy is an indigenous resource in many regions/countries worldwide and is
37 among the renewables with the greatest potential (Bahaj, 2011 and Cruz, 2008), but is still
38 almost entirely untapped. The ever-growing need for sustainable, non-polluting electricity led
39 to the development of a wide variety of technologies to harvest wave energy. This situation is
40 not expected to decrease as new concepts tend to replace those that are being abandoned.
41 However, only a few of the most promising concepts have proceeded to a demonstration
42 testing phase at a pre-commercial scale, after a comprehensive physical and numerical
43 modelling development plan, to minimize investment risks.

44 Amongst various devised wave energy converters (WEC), Oscillating Water Column (OWC)
45 devices are one of the concepts successfully deployed around the world (Clement et al. 2002)
46 which are expected to be one of the most popular WECs for viable wave energy harvesting.
47 The OWC devices are considered to be advantageous over the many other existing devices:
48 no moving parts are located in the water, the use of an air turbine eliminates the need for
49 gearboxes, there is no need to implement underwater cables in fixed onshore types, their
50 maintenance procedure is easy, there is an efficient usage of the sea space and they are
51 environment friendly. A detailed general review of the existing concepts and designs of wave
52 energy converters is available in Guedes Soares et al. (2012), Falcão (2010) and Falnes
53 (2007).

54 Investigations regarding wave power extraction from water waves have started since the
55 1970s and were concentrated on rigid body models as described by Evans (1976), Evans
56 (1981) and Mei (1976). Then, the uniform surface pressure model was implemented to
57 analyze the performance of OWC devices in which the governing equations are expressed in
58 terms of pressure on the OWC free surface and flow rate displacement by the OWC surface
59 motion (Evans, 1982). Falnes and McIver (1985) further extended that work by designing a
60 wave energy absorption system consisting of a number of oscillating bodies and internal
61 pressure distributions.

62 Several attempts have been made in recent years to explore the performance characteristics of
63 the various types of OWC devices. In this regard, Gervelas et al. (2011) presented numerical
64 and experimental predictions on a model scale OWC using the one dimensional time domain
65 model for regular and irregular waves. Ikoma et al. (2011) proposed an OWC device with an

66 artificial harbour surrounded by projecting walls to improve the efficiency of the wave power
67 absorption. They performed experiments in support of their results and, thus, provided an
68 estimate of the absorbed power by several types of OWC devices for the Japanese coast all
69 over the year. Crema et al. (2015) performed experimental investigations on OWC WECs
70 which are integrated into a very large floating structure. They assessed the influence of the
71 size of the OWC chamber, the lip draught and the turbine damping on the hydraulic efficiency
72 of the device in the both regular and random waves. López et al. (2014 a,b) conducted
73 numerical and comprehensive experimental investigations to explore turbine damping effects
74 as well as the influence of tidal conditions and wave characteristics on the performance of an
75 OWC device. López and Iglesias (2014) developed a virtual laboratory that allowed the
76 determination of the pneumatic efficiency of a given OWC working under specific conditions
77 of incident waves (wave height and period), tidal level and turbine damping. Falcão and
78 Henriques (2014) introduced a comprehensive review and investigation on the rules for
79 geometric, hydrodynamic, thermodynamic and aerodynamic similarity in model testing of
80 OWC devices.

81 As the nonlinear characteristics of the power take-off (PTO) system might have prominent
82 influences on the WEC power absorption capacity and cannot be applied in the linear
83 frequency domain analysis, Falcão et al. (2012) and Sheng et al. (2014 a,b) introduced a
84 nonlinear time domain approach and applied corresponding nonlinearities in the dynamic
85 motion equation of the oscillatory part of the WEC device.

86 Ning et al. (2015) investigated the hydrodynamic performance of an OWC wave energy
87 device using a fully nonlinear HOBEM (higher-order boundary element method). Ning et al.
88 (2016) performed an experimental campaign to analyze the influence of the bottom slope and
89 geometric parameters on the performance of the OWC device. They found that the opening
90 ratio (the ratio of cross-sectional area of the air-slot to cross-sectional area of the air chamber)
91 had a significant influence on the performance of the OWC device. They reported that the
92 bottom slope had little influence on the resonant frequency and that the optimal hydrodynamic
93 efficiency increased with the bottom slope. Anvesh et al. (2016) investigated the influence of
94 bottom sloping configuration located in front of the OWC on the performance of the device.
95 They found that as the slope of the bottom configuration increases, the waves are reflected
96 back which leads to decrease the capturing of wave energy from the PTO device.

97 Rezanejad et al. (2015 & 2016) studied the performance of two-dimensional nearshore dual
98 chamber OWC devices based on linear potential theory in flat and stepped sea bottom
99 condition. They proved that significant improvements in the primary efficiency of the device
100 can be achieved by implementing dual chambers in an OWC converter and the device
101 performance could be further improved by adding an appropriate step in the sea bottom.

102 This paper follows up on these last two works and aims to investigate the performance of an
103 OWC device using both numerical and experimental approaches. The numerical model is
104 developed based on linear wave theory in two dimensions as the experiments are also set up
105 principally based on two dimensional configurations. The standard numerical technique using
106 the two dimensional boundary integral equation method (BIEM) is used to obtain the solution
107 for the associated boundary value problem (BVP). The implemented linear numerical
108 approach establishes a straight forward solution to obtain a general prospective behaviour of
109 the device in the both regular and random waves. However, several non-linear phenomena
110 can occur (e.g. nonlinear hydrodynamic interactions, occurring vortices, influence of the
111 nonlinear power take-off systems and nonlinear air compressibility effects) in the process of
112 energy production which is linearized or neglected in the linear analysis. Hence, in order to
113 provide the detailed perception of the device performance in reality the comprehensive
114 experimental tests are carried out considering both regular and random waves. The validity of
115 the numerical results is assessed by comparing the relevant results with the results achieved
116 from experimental data for both regular and irregular waves. The work emphasizes the
117 exploration of the influence of the wave characteristics (wave height and wave period) as well
118 as turbine damping on the efficiency of the OWC wave energy converter.

119 **2. Numerical modelling**

120 **2.1. Mathematical formulation**

121 The mathematical model is based on the two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system (x,z)
122 with x – axis being the horizontal axis and z – axis being vertically upward positive. The
123 origin of the coordinate system is placed at the point of intersection of the vertical rigid wall
124 and the undisturbed free surface and hence it is situated at $x = 0$. The schematic diagram for
125 the numerical model of OWC together with its geometrical parameters is shown in Figure 1.
126 As shown in this figure, the sea bottom has a step located immediately under the OWC

127 opening. It is assumed that the water depth is equal to h_2 above the step and to h_1 outside of it
 128 and remains constant throughout the sea bed.

129 Under the linear water wave theory, the fluid is assumed to be inviscid, incompressible and
 130 the motion is irrotational and harmonic in time with angular frequency ω . Therefore, there is a
 131 velocity potential $\phi(x,z,t) = \text{Re}\{\varphi(x,z)e^{-i\omega t}\}$, with the spatial velocity potential $\varphi(x,z)$
 132 satisfying the following boundary value problem (BVP):

$$133 \quad \nabla^2 \varphi = 0, \text{ in the fluid region, } \nabla^2 \equiv \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \quad (1)$$

$$134 \quad \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial z} = 0, \text{ on the sea bottom} \quad (2)$$

$$135 \quad \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial n} = 0, \text{ on the step, rigid walls and barrier of the OWC chamber} \quad (3)$$

$$136 \quad \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial z} - K\varphi = 0, \text{ on the water free surface outside of the OWC chamber} \quad (4)$$

$$137 \quad \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial z} - K\varphi = \frac{i\omega}{\rho g} p, \text{ on the water free surface inside of the OWC chamber} \quad (5)$$

138 where $K = \omega^2/g$ and p is the complex time independent imposed pressure distribution of the
 139 form $P(t) = \text{Re}\{pe^{-i\omega t}\}$ over the internal free surface, \vec{n} is the normal unit vector, ρ is the sea
 140 water density, and g is the gravitational acceleration.

141 Following the method of Evans & Porter (1995), the total potential $\varphi(x,z)$ is decomposed into
 142 two parts as follows:

$$143 \quad \varphi = \varphi^S + \frac{i\omega p}{\rho g} \varphi^R \quad (6)$$

144 where φ^S is denoted as the scattered potential, which is associated with the scattering of a
 145 plane incident wave from $x = +\infty$ in the absence of an imposed pressure on the internal free
 146 surface and φ^R is the radiated potential, which is the solution of the radiation problem due to
 147 the pressure imposed on the internal free surface. The scattered potential φ^S satisfies Eqns. (1)
 148 – (5) with $p = 0$, while φ^R satisfies Eqns. (1) – (5) with Eqn. (5) replaced by:

$$149 \quad \frac{\partial \varphi^R}{\partial z} - K\varphi^R = 1 \quad (7)$$

150 In order to find the scattered potential φ^S , according to the diffraction theory, it is assumed
 151 that the scattered potential is the decomposition of two parts: incident potential φ^I and
 152 diffracted potential φ^D .

153 The incident wave potential does not feel the existing bodies and hence, it can be obtained
 154 analytically using simple linear water wave theory:

$$155 \quad \varphi^I = A \frac{i\omega}{k} \frac{\cosh k(h_1 + z)}{\sinh kh_1} e^{-ikx} \quad (8)$$

156 where A is the amplitude of the wave and k represents the wave number and is the real root of
 157 the wave dispersion relation:

$$158 \quad \omega^2 = gk \tanh kh_1 \quad (9)$$

159 Therefore, the rigid wall at $x = 0$ as well as the barrier and the step boundary condition for the
 160 diffracted potential φ^D takes the new form of the following formula in order to take into
 161 account the effects of the body existence on the incoming waves:

$$162 \quad \frac{\partial \varphi_D}{\partial n} = -\frac{\partial \varphi_I}{\partial n}, \text{ on the wall, step and barrier of the OWC chamber} \quad (10)$$

163 The rest of boundary conditions remain unchanged as before.

164 In addition, the Sommerfeld condition is used as the far field boundary condition in
 165 diffraction and radiation problems as follows:

$$166 \quad \frac{\partial \varphi^{D,R}}{\partial x} - ik\varphi^{D,R} = 0 \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow +\infty \quad (11)$$

167 The time harmonic induced volume flux $Q(t) = \text{Re}\{qe^{-i\omega t}\}$ across the internal free surface
 168 following Evans & Porter (1995) is given by:

$$169 \quad q = L \int_S \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial z} dx = q^S + \frac{i\omega p}{\rho g} q^R \quad (12)$$

170 where L is the width of the chamber perpendicular to the incident wave direction, and q^S and
 171 q^R are the volume fluxes across the internal free surface S in the scattering and radiation
 172 problems, respectively.

173 The volume flux q^R for the radiation problem is separated into real and imaginary parts as in
 174 Evans & Porter (1995):

$$175 \quad \frac{i\omega p}{\rho g} q^R = -(\hat{B} - i\omega \hat{A})p \quad (13)$$

176 where \hat{A} and \hat{B} are obtained as:

$$177 \quad \hat{A} = \frac{1}{\rho g} \text{Re}\{q^R\} \quad (14a)$$

$$178 \quad \hat{B} = \frac{\omega}{\rho g} \text{Im}\{q^R\} \quad (14b)$$

179 On the other hand, following Evans (1982), it is assumed that the total air volume flux
180 through the turbine is linearly proportional to the pressure drop across the internal free
181 surface. Therefore, by considering Eqns. (12-13) and taking into account linearized air
182 compressibility inside of the chamber, the following relationship can be achieved between
183 pressure and scattered volume flux after rearranging as:

$$184 \quad p = (\lambda + \hat{B} - i\omega\hat{A} - \frac{i\omega V_0}{\gamma p_a})^{-1} q^S \quad (15)$$

185 where V_0 is the air volume above internal free surface and inside of the chamber, γ is the
186 specific heat ratio of air which equals to 1.4, p_a is the atmospheric air pressure and λ has real
187 positive value and is associated with damping induced by the linear turbine to the air flow as
188 follows:

$$189 \quad q = \lambda p \quad (16)$$

190 The mean rate of work $W_{Reg.}$ done by the pressure force over one wave period of a regular
191 wave is given by (Evans, 1982):

$$192 \quad W_{Reg.} = \frac{1}{2} \lambda |p|^2 \quad (17)$$

193 The available power over one wave period of a monochromatic wave is given by:

$$194 \quad W_w = E c_g \quad (18)$$

195 where E is the total energy per wave period and c_g is the group velocity and is given by (Dean
196 & Dalrymple, 2001):

$$197 \quad E = \frac{1}{2} \rho g L A^2 \quad (19)$$

$$198 \quad c_g = \frac{1\omega}{2k} \left(1 + \frac{2kh_1}{\sinh 2kh_1} \right) \quad (20)$$

199 Thus, the primary efficiency $\eta_{Reg.}$ of the OWC device in regular waves is given by:

$$200 \quad \eta_{Reg.} = \frac{W_{Reg.}}{W_w} \quad (21)$$

201 It is proved in the previous investigations that the solutions for the radiated and scattering
202 problems are not independent from each other and hence the relation between them can be
203 expressed as follows (Falnes, 2002):

$$204 \quad |q^S|^2 = 8\hat{B}W_w \quad (22)$$

205 By substituting Eqns. (17) and (18) into Eqn. (21) and taking Eqn. (22) into account, the
206 following simplified form for the efficiency expression of the OWC device in regular waves
207 can be obtained:

$$208 \quad \eta_{Reg.} = \frac{4\lambda\hat{B}}{(\lambda + \hat{B})^2 + \omega^2\left(\hat{A} + \frac{V_0}{\gamma p_a}\right)^2} \quad (23)$$

209 which is independent of the incident wave power and only depends on radiation solution.

210 It is noteworthy to highlight that in order to estimate the maximum primary efficiency
211 $\eta_{Reg., max}$ in each wave period of the regular wave, it is enough to substitute the optimum
212 value of λ into Eqn. (23). The optimum value of λ can be evaluated as follows by applying
213 zero value to the derivative of Eqn. (23) with respect to λ :

$$214 \quad \lambda_{opt} = \sqrt{\hat{B}^2 + \omega^2\left(\hat{A} + \frac{V_0}{\gamma p_a}\right)^2} \quad (24)$$

215 Hence, substituting Eqn. (24) into Eqn. (23) leads to the expression for the maximum
216 efficiency of OWC device in regular waves as follows:

$$217 \quad \eta_{Reg., max} = \frac{2\hat{B}}{\lambda_{opt} + \hat{B}} \quad (25)$$

218 On the other hand, the method of Falcão & Rodrigues (2002) is implemented to analyze the
219 performance of the OWC device in random waves using the solutions of the radiation and
220 wave scattering problems in regular waves. In this regard, it is assumed that the local wave
221 climate may be represented by a set of sea states, each being a stationary stochastic ergodic
222 process and therefore the surface elevation being a Gaussian random variable for each sea

223 state. In this situation, the variance of the air pressure fluctuations σ_p^2 can be estimated as
 224 follows (Falcão & Rodrigues, 2002):

$$225 \quad \sigma_p^2 = \int_0^\infty S(\omega) \left| \frac{p(\omega)}{A} \right|^2 d\omega \quad (26)$$

226 where $p(\omega)$ can be obtained from Eqn. (15) and $S(\omega)$ is the one-sided wave elevation
 227 spectrum.

228 Due to linear proportionality between pressure drop across the air turbine and total volume
 229 flux through it, the instantaneous power absorbed from sea waves $W_{absorbed}$ can be obtained
 230 as:

$$231 \quad W_{absorbed} = \frac{\dot{m}P}{\rho_a} = \lambda P^2 \quad (27)$$

232 where \dot{m} is the air mass flow across the turbine, P is the instantaneous relative air pressure
 233 amongst outside and inside the chamber, and ρ_a is the air density.

234 It should be noted that since it was assumed that the system is linear and the free surface
 235 elevation can be considered as a Gaussian random parameter, both Q^s and P are also Gaussian
 236 processes. Hence, according to Eqn. (27), the average power absorbed from random waves
 237 $W_{Ran.}$ in a specific sea state can be estimated as follows (Falcão & Rodrigues, 2002):

$$238 \quad W_{Ran.} = E(W_{absorbed}) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} W_{absorbed} f(P) dP \quad (28)$$

239 where $E(W_{absorbed})$ is the expectation value of absorbed power and $f(P)$ is the probability
 240 density function of instantaneous pressure which follows the Gaussian distribution:

$$241 \quad f(P) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_p} \exp\left(-\frac{P^2}{2\sigma_p^2}\right) \quad (29)$$

242 By substituting Eqns. (27) and (29) into Eqn. (28) and solving the associated integral
 243 analytically, the mathematical expression of average absorbed power $W_{Ran.}$ can be stated in
 244 simpler form as (Falcão & Rodrigues, 2002):

$$245 \quad W_{Ran.} = \lambda \sigma_p^2 \quad (30)$$

246 Hence, it is evident from Eqn. (30) that the average power absorbed from random sea waves
 247 is solely dependent on the turbine characteristics and the variance of air pressure inside the
 248 chamber and can be calculated from the results of the frequency domain solution for regular
 249 waves.

250 On the other hand, the average primary efficiency of the OWC device in random sea waves
 251 $\eta_{Ran.}$ for specific sea state can be evaluated as follows:

$$252 \quad \eta_{Ran.} = \frac{W_{Ran.}}{\bar{W}_w} = \frac{\lambda \int_0^{\infty} S(\omega) \left| \frac{p(\omega)}{A} \right|^2 d\omega}{\bar{W}_w} \quad (31)$$

253 where \bar{W}_w is the average incident wave energy flux for the random wave and can be
 254 calculated from the spectral density by:

$$255 \quad \bar{W}_w = L\rho g \int_0^{\infty} S(\omega) c_g(\omega) d\omega \quad (32)$$

256 where $c_g(\omega)$ is the group velocity and can be calculated from Eqn. (20).

257 2.2. Method of solution

258 In this subsection, the numerical method applied for solving the associated BVP in the case of
 259 the OWC in the frequency domain is briefly described. The results of the frequency domain
 260 solution will be implemented in Eqns. (23), (25) and (31) for each frequency in order to
 261 analyze the performance of the OWC device.

262 The well-known BIEM is used to solve the radiation and diffraction problems separately. For
 263 solving the governing equation with appropriate boundary conditions using numerical
 264 approach, the distribution of all variables along the linear elements is assumed to be linear.
 265 Discretizing the Laplace equation based on the boundary element method, the fundamental
 266 integral equation for boundary points is obtained as (Paris et al. 1997):

$$267 \quad c(X)\phi(X) + \int_{\partial D} \phi(Y) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n}(X,Y) ds(Y) = \int_{\partial D} \psi(X,Y) \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial n}(Y) ds(Y) \quad (33)$$

268 where ϕ is the unknown flow potential, $\partial\phi/\partial n$ is the derivative of the potential relative to
 269 normal unit vector on the boundary, ψ is the fundamental solution of Laplace equation, and
 270 ∂D is the boundary of consideration. Eqn. (33) relates the value of the flow potential at a fixed

271 point X to each and every arbitrary point Y on the entire boundary. The value of the parameter
272 c which is called the free term depends only on the shape of the boundary and is equal to:

$$273 \quad c(X) = \frac{\alpha(X)}{2\pi} \quad (34)$$

274 where $\alpha(X)$ is the angle between the two tangents of the boundary domain in the left and right
275 hand sides of the point X .

276 The multi region concept is used to discretise the linear fundamental integral Eqn. (33), which
277 diminishes the numerical errors arising from the small thickness of the front wall of the OWC
278 device (see Rezanejad et al., 2013 & 2015 for details).

279 **3. Experimental investigation**

280 **3.1. Physical model**

281 The model for the shore line fixed OWC was built with the scale factor of 1:25 ($\varepsilon = 1/25$) to
282 carry out the experimental campaign. The sketch of the model with its main dimensions as
283 well as the tested physical one in the wave flume is illustrated in Figure 2. A Guarda region
284 located in North West of Spain would be one of the appropriate locations to install prototype
285 of the OWC examined in the present study, as reported by López et al., (2013) for the OWC
286 with similar dimensions but with the different immersion depth of the lip. As the model was
287 designed in such a way that occupied the whole width of the wave flume, the results achieved
288 from the experimental campaign would be recognized as a 2D case and hence could be
289 compared with the results gathered from the numerical solutions.

290 The following three main non-dimensional values have a dominant influence on the primary
291 performance of OWC devices: Froude number (Fr), Reynolds number (Re) and
292 dimensionless pressure. The Froude and Reynolds similarities cannot be satisfied
293 simultaneously. In the model testing of floating objects, the effects due to variations in Froude
294 number are almost always much more important than those associated with changes in
295 Reynolds number (Falcão and Henriques, 2014). This is mainly due to the reason that a
296 relative large Reynolds number in a scale model can be easily achieved in most practical cases
297 and thus the viscous terms in the fluid momentum equation will become minor (see Sheng et
298 al., 2014c for further details). Although the OWC studied here is not a floating OWC, the
299 statement that changes in Froude number imply larger changes in the model similarity than

300 those related to changes in the Reynolds number, still remain a valid. Hence, Froude number
301 was kept on the basis of the lessons learnt in previous studies and Reynolds number was
302 ignored as a modelling rule. It should be noted that it is required to consider large quantities
303 of air volume inside the OWC chamber if the dimensionless pressure is intended to be applied
304 as a criterion to perform the experiments simultaneously with considering Froude similarity
305 rule, but it is normally applicable for large model testing conditions and hence the simulation
306 of the air compressibility effects was ignored in the experimental setup used for this study.
307 Following the Froude similarity rule, the scale ratios for the most important parameters
308 implemented in this paper are shown in Table 1.

309 As illustrated in Figure 2, the model was built from Plexiglas material due to its appropriate
310 mechanical strength, simplicity in construction procedure and transparency which allowed the
311 observation of the motions of the inside water free surface. In general, scaling ratios in wave
312 energy converter model tests do not exceed 1:10 and hence leads to power ratio of about
313 1:3200 (see Table 1). In the case of an OWC wave energy converter, this scale is too small for
314 the turbine to be adequately simulated by a mini-turbine. Hence, the usual procedure is to
315 simulate the power take-off unit as an orifice or as a layer of porous material to apply the
316 equivalent influence of the impulse or Wells turbine, respectively (Falcão and Henriques,
317 2014). The reason being that pressure drop across the orifice or the porous medium element
318 varies quadratically or linearly with the flow rate, as it does across an impulse or Wells
319 turbine, respectively (López et al. 2014b). The early developments of OWC technology were
320 focused on Wells turbines; over the last years, however, research has been mainly directed
321 toward impulse turbines (López et al. 2014b). Hence, the impulse turbine is selected here in
322 this study as the power take-off unit acting on the OWC system. In this paper, the rectangular
323 slot (instead of a circular orifice) was implemented in the top of the model to provide a more
324 realistic 2D condition in the experiments. In this regard, two different slot widths ($e = 1$ and
325 2.5 mm) were applied to the model to impose high and low turbine damping conditions,
326 respectively. The ratio of the cross sectional area of the slot to the water free surface area
327 (OWC area) inside the chamber is consequently equal to 0.78% and 2% for the high and low
328 damping conditions ($e = 1$ and 2.5 mm), respectively. In principle, the 1 mm slot width was
329 chosen in the experimental setup based on the past investigations which reported the best
330 performance of the OWC devices are mainly achieved when the slot area is around 1% of the
331 cross sectional area of the OWC (e.g. Ashlin et al., 2016 illustrated that the best energy
332 absorption is obtained when the slot area is about 0.68% of the OWC area). Furthermore, the

333 low damping condition ($e = 2.5$ mm) is also investigated in the experimental part of this
334 research study to explore the performance of the OWC device in various wave characteristics
335 when the appropriate desired damping condition could not be imposed to the system.

336 **3.2. Experimental setup and test design**

337 The experimental tests were carried out in the wave flume of the University of Santiago de
338 Compostela which is 20 m long, 0.65 m wide and 0.95 m high. The flume has a piston-type
339 wave generator with Active Wave Absorption Control System (AWACS) which has the
340 capability to produce both regular and irregular waves. The sketch of the wave flume as well
341 as the location of the corresponding wave gauge sensors and the OWC model is shown in
342 Figure 3. As can be seen, the OWC model was located at 10.75 m distance from the mid-
343 position of the wave paddle and occupied the whole width of the wave flume. Hence, the
344 generated waves were not impressed by the wave dissipation ramp as some part of their
345 energy were absorbed by the OWC model and the rest were reflected back to the wave
346 generator upon interfacing with the model. As the wave generator system was equipped with
347 the AWACS system, the reflected waves were absorbed automatically by the wave generator
348 which eventually caused the incident wave pattern to remain undisturbed.

349 In order to detect water free surface elevation outside of the OWC model, eight resistive wave
350 gauges were installed in the wave flume, three of which were located on the front wall of the
351 OWC model, and the remaining mounted along the wave flume as shown in Figure 3. Three
352 ultra-sonic wave sensors (shown in Figure 2) were installed inside the chamber of the OWC
353 model (in the middle, left and right hand sides of the model) as well as one air pressure gauge
354 sensor. The sampling frequency of all sensors was 20 Hz. The WG1 sensor was installed to
355 detect the incident wave pattern at the beginning of each test before the reflected waves
356 approach this sensor. The data gathered from the wave gauges WG3, WG4 and WG5 were
357 used to analyse the incident and reflected wave characteristics during each experiment and the
358 data measured from WG2 were considered as an alternative option for cases when disturbance
359 or any interruption is occurred in those wave gauges. The data measured from the wave
360 gauges WG6, WG7 and WG8 were used to be compared with the measurements of the ultra-
361 sonic sensors.

362 Eventually, the data measured from the three ultra-sonic sensors and pressure gauges were
363 used to evaluate the energy absorbed from the incoming waves. In this regard, the free surface

364 elevation ζ measured by the ultra-sonic sensor located in the middle of the OWC model (US2)
 365 and wave gauge WG1 as well as air pressure measured by the pressure gauge sensor (PS) are
 366 illustrated in Figure 4 for the regular waves with the period and height equal to 1.8 s and 0.04
 367 m, respectively. As can be seen in Figure 4, the wave amplitude increases gradually between
 368 the time instants $t = 10$ and 15 seconds and remains constant after $t = 15$ s, which is due to
 369 the approach of the reflected waves to the sensor (WG1) along with the incident waves
 370 generated by the paddle. It is also evident from Figure 4 that the amplitude of the free surface
 371 oscillations inside the OWC model as well as the amplitude of the pressure become stable and
 372 tend to have a constant value after the time instant around $t = 8$ s, which proves the
 373 appropriate action of the AWACS system to absorb the reflected waves in the wave flume.

374 The OWC device was tested in both regular and irregular wave conditions. Two different
 375 damping conditions (high and low damping) were applied to the model by changing the slot
 376 width on the cap of the model. The slot width for the high and low damping conditions was
 377 adjusted as to be 1 and 2.5 mm, respectively. The water depth was set to 0.42 m and was kept
 378 constant during all the experiments. For the regular wave tests, ten wave periods ($T = 1, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8, 2.0, 2.2, 2.4, 2.6$ and 2.8 s) and three wave heights ($H = 0.02, 0.04$
 379 and 0.06 m) were combined. The duration of each test was designed in such a way that at
 380 least 100 individual waves were generated. In the irregular wave tests, four peak wave period
 381 ($T_p = 1.54, 1.98, 2.42$ and 2.86 s) with significant wave height of $H_s = 0.04$ m were applied.
 382 In addition, in the case of high damping condition, the model was tested in irregular waves
 383 with the significant wave height of $H_s = 0.08$ m, too. Hence, 72 tests (60 tests in regular and
 384 12 tests in irregular wave condition) were, in total, carried out to evaluate the performance of
 385 the device. The duration of each irregular wave test was defined so that at least 500 waves
 386 were generated. The irregular wave condition was generated in the flume based on the
 387 JONSWAP spectrum, which can be expressed as:

$$389 \quad S(\omega) = g^2 \omega^{-5} \exp \left\{ -1.25 \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_p} \right)^{-4} \right\} \Gamma^{\exp \left(-\frac{(\omega - \omega_p)^2}{2(\sigma \omega_p)^2} \right)} \quad (35)$$

390 where ω_p is the peak angular frequency ($\omega_p = 2\pi/T_p$), Γ is the peak-enhancement factor and
 391 was set to 3.3, and σ is the shape parameter and is defined as:

$$392 \quad \sigma = \begin{cases} \sigma_a = 0.07, & \omega \leq \omega_p \\ \sigma_b = 0.09, & \omega > \omega_p \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

393 3.3. Data analysis

394 The performance of the OWC device can be evaluated by estimating the incident wave power
 395 and the power absorbed from waves. The average power absorbed from regular waves $W_{Reg.}$
 396 or random waves $W_{Ran.}$ can be determined using experimental data as follows:

$$397 \quad W_{Reg.} \text{ or } W_{Ran.} = \frac{1}{t_{max}} \int_0^{t_{max}} P Q dt \quad (37)$$

398 where t_{max} is the duration of the test, P is the air pressure inside the OWC chamber measured
 399 by the pressure gauge sensor and Q is the air volume flux through the slot of the OWC model.
 400 The air flow can be assumed as an incompressible flow due to the small volume of air trapped
 401 inside of the model. Hence, the air volume flux Q can be estimated implementing the water
 402 free surface elevation ζ_i inside of the OWC detected by the three ultra-sonic sensors installed
 403 inside the model as follows:

$$404 \quad Q = LbD^3(\zeta_i) \quad (38)$$

405 where L is the width of the chamber perpendicular to the incident wave direction, b is the
 406 length of the chamber (parallel to the incident wave direction) and $D^3(\zeta_i)$ is the third-order
 407 approximation to the time derivative of the free surface elevation which can be expressed as
 408 follows:

$$409 \quad D^3(\zeta_i) = \frac{-11\zeta_i + 18\zeta_{i+1} - 9\zeta_{i+2} + 2\zeta_{i+3}}{6\Delta t} \quad (39)$$

410 where $\Delta t = 0.05$ s is the time step between two consecutive data points.

411 It should be noted that the free surface elevation ζ_i inside the OWC chamber at time t_i , is
 412 calculated by means of averaging the data gathered from the three ultra-sonic sensors at each
 413 time instant.

414 In order to determine the incident wave power for both regular and random waves, the data
 415 measured by the wave gauges WG3, WG4 and WG5 are used to estimate the energy spectrum
 416 of the incoming waves. As part of the incoming waves is always reflected upon intercepting

417 the model, the data measured by the wave gauges are the combination of both incoming and
418 reflected waves. In this regard, the method of Mansard and Funke (1980) is used to
419 decompose incoming and reflected wave data from each other and on that basis the energy
420 spectrum of the incoming waves is determined. It is noteworthy to remark that Viviano et al.
421 (2016) reported that the accuracy level of this method is satisfactorily enough to estimate the
422 incident and reflected wave pattern and hence could be reliably used here in the analysis
423 procedure. In this context, figure 5 illustrates an example of incident and reflected water
424 elevation spectra achieved by applying the method of Mansard and Funke (1980) for the case
425 of regular wave with $T = 1.2\text{ s}$ and $H = 0.02\text{ m}$. Both spectra are perfectly narrow banded
426 (which correspond to the single frequency of the regular wave) and their spiked peaks occur at
427 $\omega = 5.24 \frac{\text{Rad}}{\text{s}}$ which is consistent perfectly with the applied wave period $T = 1.2\text{ s}$ to the wave
428 maker device. The ratio of the reflected wave energy to the incident wave energy is one of the
429 possible alternatives to estimate the performance of the device which is avoided to use here as
430 some part of the energy is always lost due to occurring viscous phenomena. Hence, only the
431 incident wave spectra as well as the data recorded from ultra-sonic sensors and air pressure
432 gauge are used to estimate the captured and incident wave power. In this regard, by
433 substituting the associated incoming wave spectrum S into Eqn. (32), the average incident
434 wave power can be calculated for both regular and random wave conditions. By determining
435 both incident wave power and absorbed power by the OWC device, the efficiency of the
436 device can be estimated using Eqns. (21) and (31) for regular and random waves, respectively.

437 **4. Results and discussion**

438 In this section, the results obtained from numerical modelling and experimental studies of the
439 OWC model with characteristics shown in the Figure 2 are presented. In both numerical and
440 experimental approaches, the focus is mostly on the evaluation of the performance of the
441 OWC in regular and random waves. Furthermore, the validity of the numerical approach was
442 evaluated by comparing the corresponding results with the results achieved from the
443 experimental study.

444 In spite of the typical fixed and floating structures which are strived in their design procedure
445 to prevent the occurrence of any resonance phenomenon, the resonance mechanism arisen
446 from the hydrodynamic interaction of the incident waves with the water column inside the
447 OWC device can improve the efficiency of the device. In principle, two different possible

448 resonance phenomena can occur in the conventional fixed type OWC devices. The first
 449 resonance mechanism, which is the dominant one, occurs due to the adaption of the frequency
 450 of the incoming waves and the natural frequency of the water column inside the chamber of
 451 the OWC. By the occurrence of this resonance phenomenon, the performance of the OWC
 452 device tends to be maximized.

453 In this regard, the associated angular frequency can be estimated to be approximately equal to:

$$454 \quad \omega = \sqrt{\frac{g}{a}} \quad (40)$$

455 where a is the length of immersion of the OWC device and g is the acceleration due to
 456 gravity. The above mentioned formula is developed using the simple hydrostatic balance
 457 equations by considering the water inside the OWC as a rigid piston. It gives satisfactory
 458 predictions when the water column inside the enclosed volume of the OWC is narrow and
 459 hence has a reciprocating motion similar to a piston due to the action of the incoming waves
 460 (Evans and Porter, 1995 and Rezanejad et al., 2013). In the OWC model studied in this paper
 461 (shown in Figure 2), the approximate angular frequency of the first resonance phenomenon is
 462 predicted to be equal to $\omega \cong 12.8 \text{ Rad/s}$ ($T \cong 0.5 \text{ s}$) implementing Eqn. (40). The added mass
 463 of the water column inside the OWC chamber is neglected in simplified formulation
 464 introduced in the Eqn. (40) which may cause significant discrepancies to occur amongst
 465 obtained predictions and realistic conditions. In this regard, van't Veer and Tholen (2008)
 466 introduced an approximate expression to estimate the angular frequency of the first resonance
 467 condition by considering the influence of the added mass as follows:

$$468 \quad \omega = \sqrt{\frac{g}{a + 0.41\sqrt{S}}} \quad (41)$$

469 where S is the sectional area of the OWC chamber. Hence, the resonant angular frequency of
 470 the studied OWC is predicted by Eqn. (41) to be equal to $\omega \cong 7.5 \text{ Rad/s}$ ($T \cong 0.84 \text{ s}$).

471 The second resonance mechanism occurs when the incident wave frequency is such that the
 472 fluid inside the chamber is excited into an anti-symmetric sloshing mode. The appropriate
 473 condition for the occurrence of this phenomenon can approximately be associated with cases
 474 when $kb = n\pi$, where n is the sloshing mode number. It should be noted that the accuracy
 475 level of the above mentioned formula is improved by increasing the submergence length of
 476 the OWC. Therefore, the first mode of the sloshing resonance phenomenon occurs

477 approximately in the incident wave length of 25.6 cm (equivalent to $T \cong 0.4$ s) for the case of
 478 the OWC model investigated in this paper. The wave length for the occurrence of the higher
 479 modes of the sloshing phenomenon is even shorter than the first mode and does not lie in the
 480 generation range of the paddle. Hence, the second resonance mechanism which is dedicated to
 481 the sloshing phenomenon is not expected to occur in the OWC model considered in this study.

482 **4.1. Comparison between experimental and numerical results**

483 The primary efficiency of the OWC device is one of the most prominent issues that should be
 484 considered in the design procedure of the OWC devices. The primary efficiency, which is
 485 termed here as the efficiency or performance of the OWC device, indicates the percentage of
 486 the incident wave energy converted to pneumatic energy. In this section, the performance of
 487 the OWC model shown in Figure 2 was estimated using numerical and experimental methods
 488 following the approaches introduced in Sections 2 and 3. In this regard, Figure 6 illustrates
 489 the efficiency of the OWC model $\eta_{Reg.}$ in regular waves with respect to the incident wave
 490 period, which was obtained from the numerical simulation and the experimental tests for low
 491 and high damping conditions. The wave height was equal to $H = 2$ cm in the associated
 492 experimental tests and slot width was equal to $e = 1$ and 2.5 mm for the high and low
 493 damping conditions, respectively. It is noteworthy to remark that the calculated performance
 494 is not dependent on the wave height in the numerical approach as the linear wave theory was
 495 implemented in formulating the problem. The least squares method was implemented in the
 496 numerical approach to determine the appropriate linear turbine damping coefficient λ in such
 497 a way that the calculated performance had the best fit to the corresponding experimental data.
 498 In order to find the damping coefficient λ associated with the damping of the PTO system, the
 499 efficiency of the OWC is assessed in regular waves (using Eqn. 23) for a range of damping
 500 values varying between 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} $m^4.s/kg$ with the evenly distributed increments equal
 501 to 10^{-7} $m^4.s/kg$. The discrepancies occurred between obtained numerical and experimental
 502 results for the each set of damping values are calculated and the least squares method was
 503 applied to assess the goodness of the each fit. Eventually, the damping coefficient dedicated
 504 to the best fitted line is considered as a damping of the system for the each low and high
 505 damping case. Following this approach, the linear damping coefficients were estimated to be
 506 equal to 1.208×10^{-4} and 5.072×10^{-4} $m^4.s/kg$ for high and low damping conditions,
 507 respectively, and were kept as a fixed parameter in the rest of the numerical calculations. On
 508 the other hand, the damping coefficient corresponds in principle to the assumed linear

509 relationship between the air volume flux (q) and pressure (p) (Eqn. 16). As was explained
510 earlier, the damping coefficient λ is estimated here using the indirect method based on
511 approaching the best fit between the numerically and experimentally calculated efficiency
512 curves. However, the estimated damping coefficients are also expected to be consistent with
513 the general trend of air flux and air pressure variations in each instant. In this regard, Figure 7
514 shows the variation of the air flux and pressure inside the OWC chamber obtained from the
515 regular wave test with the $T = 1.2$ s and $H = 0.02$ m for the high and low damping
516 conditions. Although the pressure drop is in principle proportional to the square of the flow
517 rate passing through the orifice, however, as can be seen here in the figure 7, the damping
518 lines (plotted based on the estimated damping coefficients) are also in a satisfactory
519 agreement with the experimental data. It should be also remarked that to plot the damping
520 lines, the estimated linear damping coefficients 1.208×10^{-4} and 5.072×10^{-4} $m^4.s/kg$
521 are multiplied to the OWC width, $L = 0.61$ m, as they were estimated based on the 2D
522 calculations (the width of the device perpendicular to the wave direction is assumed to have
523 the unit value).

524 As can be seen in Figure 6, the agreement between numerical and experimental predictions
525 for both damping conditions is satisfactory. Furthermore, the maximum theoretical efficiency
526 $\eta_{Reg,max}$ determined from Eqn. (25) is shown in this figure. The maximum efficiency takes
527 the unity value at the period of $T = 0.75$ s which corresponds to the first resonance
528 mechanism. As explained in the previous section, the simplified formula of Eqn. (40) predicts
529 the value of 0.5 s for the period of the maximum efficiency, which has a difference to the
530 value obtained from the numerical simulations. The difference between predictions obtained
531 from these two methods is mainly due to ignoring the share of the added mass in this
532 formulation. On the other hand, the formula introduced in Eqn. (41) gives more precise
533 prediction regarding the resonance period of OWC (which is $T = 0.84$ s as explained earlier
534 in the section 4) as the role of the added mass is included in the proposed formulation.

535 As can be expected, the OWC model has higher performance in high damping condition than
536 in low damping case and the maximum efficiency is not unity for both damping conditions.
537 The maximum efficiency of both high and low damping conditions occurs almost in the same
538 period of the peak of the maximum efficiency curve, which proves that the period for which
539 the first resonance mechanism takes place is not dependent on the damping condition, and is
540 mostly determined by the natural frequency of the water column. As was predicted in the

541 previous section, none of the efficiency curves contain the secondary peak due to the
542 occurrence of the sloshing phenomenon. The maximum efficiency curve $\eta_{Reg.,max}$ shown in
543 Figure 6 in principle represents the threshold of the power absorption capacity of the current
544 geometrical configuration of the system. Hence, it can be concluded that the performance of
545 the system in the case of high damping condition is satisfactory in the small and medium
546 wave periods as the corresponding efficiency has almost slight decrease with respect to the
547 maximum efficiency curve. On the other hand, the efficiency of the system decreases
548 significantly with respect to the maximum efficiency in large wave periods. Furthermore, the
549 efficiency curve has an undesirable drop almost in the whole range of wave periods in the low
550 damping condition which leads to the essential decrease in the power production of the
551 system rather than the optimized condition.

552 Figure 8 illustrates the efficiency of the OWC model in random waves $\eta_{Ran.}$ with respect to
553 the peak wave period for both low and high damping conditions. The random waves are
554 generated using the JONSWAP spectrum in both numerical and experimental approaches.
555 Also, the optimized efficiency of the OWC model in random waves obtained from the
556 numerical simulation is introduced in this figure. In order to estimate the optimized efficiency,
557 the damping of the OWC model is considered to have a fixed value in each sea state which is
558 determined by Eqn. (24) for the equivalent regular wave with the period equal to the T_e
559 (energy period in random waves). It should be noted that basically there is no analytical
560 method devised yet for estimating the optimized damping coefficient in irregular waves (Bull,
561 2015 and Sheng and Lewis, 2016) as random waves are composed of individual wave
562 components with various frequencies. However, the efficiency calculated based of the above
563 mentioned approach will be called here as “optimized efficiency” since the damping of the
564 system in each sea state is chosen to have the constant value equal to the optimum damping
565 value of the equivalent regular wave. The two low and high damping coefficients determined
566 in the regular wave analysis procedure are considered to remain unchanged in the random
567 wave analysis. As is evident in Figure 8, both numerical and experimental approaches
568 produce consistent results. The efficiency curve in random waves follows in general the same
569 trend of variations as in the regular waves. However, it is slightly smoother in random waves
570 which can be related to the nature of the irregular waves that contain various individual
571 waves. Similarly to the regular wave condition, the efficiency of the OWC model in random
572 waves is higher for the high damping condition and is almost close to the optimized efficiency
573 curve. It should be noted that the optimized efficiency curve is probably not the maximum

574 efficiency that could be captured from the random waves and it would be possible to improve
575 the performance of the system by the application of an appropriate active control procedure
576 for the turbine damping characteristics.

577 4.2. OWC primary efficiency: effect of the damping and incident wave period

578 The numerically estimated performance of the OWC model in regular wave conditions versus
579 the wave period and turbine damping coefficient are illustrated in Figure 9. As can be
580 detected from this figure, both wave period and turbine damping coefficient have the
581 dominant influence on the performance of the device and hence should be considered as most
582 prominent parameters to design an OWC device for a specific wave climate. It can also be
583 observed that the occurrence period of the maximum efficiency in each specific turbine
584 damping occurs approximately for the same wave period ($T = 0.75$ s) as reported in the
585 previous section too.

586 As is evident in Figure 9, the absolute maximum efficiency of the OWC model is less
587 sensitive to the small variations in the turbine damping coefficient. Therefore, the damping
588 coefficient can be chosen in the range of 1.5×10^{-4} to $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^4 \cdot \text{s}/\text{kg}$ in order to
589 capture over 90 percent of the incoming wave energy with the period around 0.75 s which is
590 an appropriate point in the design procedure of the turbine control system. The efficiency of
591 the device significantly drops for large wave periods and just for the small ranges of the
592 turbine damping coefficient (between 1.2×10^{-5} to $3.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^4 \cdot \text{s}/\text{kg}$) it approaches the
593 value around 20 percent. As the waves with large periods contain large amount of energy, it is
594 essential to set up the turbine in such a way that imposes appropriate damping to the system to
595 absorb the energy of waves. Otherwise the waves would be reflected back to the sea upon
596 encountering the device without their energy being captured.

597 It should be noted that the abrupt drop of the efficiency outside of the above mentioned range
598 of the damping coefficient is due to the small magnitude of the conductance parameter \hat{B} in
599 large wave periods (Rezanejad et al., 2013) which causes the numerator of the efficiency
600 expression in Eqn. (23) to tend to have a zero value while the denominator could remain as a
601 non-zero value due to the influence of the turbine damping coefficient λ . Hence, the efficiency
602 of the device tends to have a small value in the large wave periods and in the extensive ranges
603 of turbine damping coefficient.

604 The curve showing the respective values of the optimum turbine damping on which the
605 maximum efficiency occurs in each wave period is also shown in Figure 9 by the solid black
606 line. It can be seen from Figure 9 that the variation of the optimum turbine damping is small
607 for the wave periods larger than two seconds and could be considered as a fixed value
608 (approximately equal to $3.6 \times 10^{-5} m^4.s/kg$) and hence the control tool installed in the
609 device should only impose this amount of damping to the system to maximize energy
610 absorption of the device. On the other hand, there is significant variation in the optimum
611 turbine damping for waves with periods less than two seconds (in the range of 0.5×10^{-4} to
612 $3 \times 10^{-4} m^4.s/kg$) and hence the control system should alter the damping of the turbine
613 under the action of the changings occurring in the incident wave period.

614 **4.3. OWC primary efficiency: effect of the incident wave height**

615 In order to discern the influence of the wave height on the performance of the OWC device,
616 three different wave heights ($H = 0.02, 0.04$ and $0.06 m$) in regular waves as well as two
617 significant wave heights ($H_s = 0.04$ and $0.08 m$) are applied in the experimental campaign.
618 Figure 10 illustrates the variations of the OWC efficiency with respect to the wave period for
619 the three individual wave heights in the regular wave condition as well as the results achieved
620 from numerical approach. The results shown in Figure 10 only correspond to the high
621 damping condition, whereas the respective results of the low damping case are introduced in
622 Figure 11. It is evident in these figures that the relation of the wave height to the efficiency of
623 the device is more complex. As can be seen in Figure 10, higher wave height results in higher
624 efficiency of the device in large wave periods ($T \geq 1.6s$) and on the contrary, results in lower
625 performance for small periods of the incoming waves ($T \leq 1.2s$) in high damping condition.
626 In other words, as wave height increases, the efficiency curve of the device tends to have a
627 smoother variation with respect to the wave period.

628 Hence, the numerical results obtained from linear modelling of the device should be used
629 cautiously for large wave heights as a significant deviation between numerical predictions and
630 real condition could arise. On the other hand, increasing the wave height enhances the
631 performance of the OWC device in the low damping condition regardless of the variations in
632 wave period as can be seen in Figure 11. In order to better understand the impact of the wave
633 height by simultaneously considering the variations of the wave period, the efficiency of the
634 OWC model is presented in Figure 12 for both high and low damping conditions in regular

635 waves. In general, it can be concluded that the influence of the wave height is of lesser
636 significance on the efficiency of the OWC model than on the wave period, although it would
637 become a prominent parameter as the damping of the system increases.

638 A similar behaviour is also detected for the random waves, as can be observed in Figure 13.
639 This figure corresponds to the high turbine damping condition. Similarly to the regular wave
640 condition, higher significant wave height results in higher efficiency in larger periods and
641 lower efficiency in smaller ones, although the rate of variation is not as significant as in
642 regular waves which is due to the occurrence of various wave periods in each sea state.

643 **5. Conclusions**

644 The performance of the Oscillating Water Column (OWC) device was studied in this paper
645 based on both numerical and experimental approaches. A 2D linear model is developed in the
646 numerical approach and the results achieved from the frequency domain analysis are used to
647 estimate the efficiency of the device in both regular and random wave conditions. A
648 comprehensive set of experiments is carried out in regular and random wave conditions in
649 order to evaluate the accuracy level of the numerical method as well as to investigate the
650 influence of the turbine damping, wave height and period.

651 It is observed in both numerical and experimental results that the wave period and turbine
652 damping have a dominant influence on the performance of the device and hence ought to be
653 in the focus of attention in the optimizing procedure of the OWC device. The performance of
654 the device drops significantly in high wave periods and becomes very sensitive to the
655 variation of the turbine damping. The absolute maximum efficiency of the device mainly
656 depends on the wave period and becomes less sensitive to the minor variations imposed to the
657 optimum value of the turbine damping. The influence of the wave height on the performance
658 of the OWC device is of lesser importance as compared to the two other parameters (wave
659 period and turbine damping) and causes the efficiency curve become smoother with respect to
660 the variations of wave period.

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Table 1: Scale factor for various parameters based on the Froude criterion

Parameter	Unit	Scale factor for $\varepsilon = 25$
Wave amplitude, A	m	$\varepsilon = 25$
Wave period, T	s	$\varepsilon^{0.5} = 5$
Wave angular frequency, ω	Rad/s	$\varepsilon^{-0.5} = 0.2$
Pressure, P	N/m^2	$\varepsilon = 25$
Volume flux, q	m^3/s	$\varepsilon^{2.5} = 3125$
Power, W_w	$N.m/s$	$\varepsilon^{3.5} = 78125$
Efficiency, η	-	$\varepsilon = 1$

Figure 1: Sketch diagram for the numerical model of the OWC

Figure 2: Physical model of the OWC device

Figure 3: Sketch of the experimental setup

Figure 4: Data measured by the wave gauge WG1, ultra-sonic US2 and air pressure gauge sensors for the regular waves with the period and height equal to 1.8 s and 0.04 m

Figure 5: Incident and reflected spectra for the regular wave with $T = 1.2$ s and $H = 0.02$ m achieved by applying method of Mansard and Funke (1980) to the experimental data

Figure 6: Efficiency of the OWC model in regular waves ($H = 2$ cm) with respect to the wave period achieved from experimental tests and numerical simulation

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: The air volume flux Q versus air pressure P achieved from the regular wave test with $H = 2$ cm and $T = 1.2$ s as well as the damping line (plotted based on the estimated linear damping coefficient) for the high (a) and low (b) damping cases

Figure 8: Efficiency of the OWC model in random waves (JONSWAP spectrum with $H_s = 4 \text{ cm}$) with respect to the peak wave period achieved from experimental tests and numerical simulation

Figure 9: Efficiency of the OWC model in regular waves with respect to the wave period and turbine damping coefficient achieved from the numerical simulation

Figure 10: Efficiency of the OWC model in regular waves with respect to the wave period for the three individual wave heights as well as the results obtained from numerical simulation (high turbine damping condition)

Figure 11: Efficiency of the OWC model in regular waves with respect to the wave period for the three individual wave heights as well as the results obtained from numerical simulation (low turbine damping condition)

Figure 12: Efficiency of the OWC model in regular waves versus to the wave period and height for the high and low damping conditions

Figure 13: Efficiency of the OWC model in random waves with respect to the peak wave period for the two individual significant wave heights as well as the results obtained from numerical simulation (high turbine damping condition)